

Evaluating a Nurse Practitioner-led Telehealth for Medicare Advantage Program (THV-MA)

Kelley Scott, DNP, APRN, FNP-C

Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC -- Elizabeth Winokur, Ph.D., RN, CEN

Background

- COVID-19 further reduced access to healthcare and increased care gaps especially in the older adult population
- Care gaps are defined as failing to keep up to date with recommended preventive care
- A large California health system launched the Telehealth for Medicare Advantage Program (THV-MA) to address Medicare Advantage patients' healthcare access issues and care gaps
- The literature supports the need for telehealth programs to be evaluated using a standard format to ensure that the processes in place are producing the intended outcomes

Purpose Statement

To evaluate the effectiveness of the existing Telehealth for Medicare Advantage program

Goals

- Increase access to care options
- Close care gaps
- Have satisfied patients

Conceptual Framework

- The Logic Model provides structure for evaluating programs
- Helps depict the relationships between the process and the intended outcomes

Methods

- **Design:** Program evaluation using Logic Model framework and STEM Domains to determine the effectiveness of meeting the THV-MA program goals: increased access to care, care gap closure, and patient satisfaction
- **Setting:** Large, non-profit healthcare system in CA
- **Target Population:** Adult patients aged 65 and older with Medicare Advantage coverage who completed a synchronous video visit in the THV-MA program

Results

Access to Care

- 3,021 patients called
- 164 Appointments Scheduled
- 119 patients completed a THV

Barriers to Access

- Overall, 278 patients (10%) had a barrier resulting in not scheduling a THV
- Appointment not scheduled due to No smart device correlated with increased age

Care Gaps

- 94% patient had 1 or more care gaps closed
- No difference detected with age or gender and gap closure

Patient Satisfaction

- High satisfaction ranging 3.4-3.7 on Likert scale
- Most common description by patients was that the MA-THV was thorough

Conclusions

- THV-MA increases
 - Access to care
 - Assessment of chronic conditions
 - Screening test completion
- THV-MA associated with high patient satisfaction

Limitations

- Lack of staff
- Short evaluation period
- Person who administered the patient satisfaction survey was not bilingual

Recommendations

- Continue the THV-MA program
- Explore ways to reduce barriers to THV
- Examine potential savings of referring patients with positive fall risk screening to physical therapy to prevent costly hip fractures
- Analyze financial impact of addressing and closing CMS-HCC (Hierarchical Condition Categories) condition gaps
- Consider hiring more outreach coordinators to increase ability to make repeated attempts to reach those who had no answer, or a voicemail was left

References

